

Interdisciplinary contents integration and key competences developed in a project work of Industrial Engineering and Management third year

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Abstract

The traditional curricular structure of organizing courses adopted by many university programmes is not suitable for the students to relate and integrate different interdisciplinary contents. The main consequence of this fixed structure is the students' difficulty of applying these contents in an integrated way to develop a project or just to solve a problem. Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) programme from the University of Minho, Portugal, is, for a long time, trying to break this paradigm. So, it implements Project-Based Learning (PBL) in three semesters in a five-year programme (ten semesters). Attending to the small sample (three in ten semesters) much more can be done and it does not have to be all the semesters PBL. This was the motivation for the authors of this paper to propose a common project between two courses of the IEM third year, first semester (IEM31): Production Systems Organization I and Process Control and Automation. These two courses have in common the need to design production systems and/or industrial applications to be integrated into these. The main project work objectives were to design a virtual or real-world automated production line/cell and simulate it using a hands-on activity and a cell mock-up in the classroom. Students were organized into teams of seven to ten members. This research was based on a qualitative research (case study) approach through the analysis of an on-line questionnaire. Therefore, the students' feedback to the hands-on activity was registered through the on-line questionnaire and each response was classified to address the key competencies developed by the students. The paper objectives are twofold: 1) describe the teamwork outcomes, showing the contents integration of the two courses and 2) discuss the questionnaire results, highlighting the key competences acquired. This interdisciplinary experience was implemented in two editions (2017_18 and 2019_20) and the students' feedback was very positive in both editions.

Keywords: Industrial Engineering and Management Education; Active Learning; Project work; Hands-on activities.

1 Introduction

The traditional compartmentalized way of course organization do not provided a satisfactory way for engineering students to develop their profession. The engineering students need a holistic view of the system that enables the connections between bodies of knowledge (Flumerfelt et al., 2014). According to Grasso and Martinelli (2007): *"In this evolving world, a new kind of engineer is needed, one who can think broadly across disciplines and consider the human dimensions that are at the heart of every design challenge. In the new order, narrow engineering thinking will not be enough."*

At the same time, engineering students need to be always open to learn, as the world is continuously changing and needing different technologies. In this position they need to learning to learn that has been a concern since last century (Hounsell, 1979). According to UNESCO (2015), due to the volume of information now available on the internet, this was never as important as it is today.

Nevertheless, to have this profile, an engineering student should have competencies. Competencies are more than knowledge and skills (Rychen & Salganik, 2000). It also implies attitudes, recommended the Council of the European Union (Council of the European Union, 2018). Knowledge is related to facts and figures, concepts, ideas and theories which are already established and support the understanding of a certain area or subject. Skills are the ability and capacity to carry out processes and use the existing knowledge to achieve results. Attitudes are the disposition and mind-sets to act or react to ideas, persons or situations (Council of the European Union, 2018, p. 14). This council defined eight key competencies: 1) Literacy; 2) Multilingual; 3) Mathematical, science, technology and engineering; 4) Digital; 5) Personal, social and learning to learn; 6)

Citizenship; 7) Entrepreneurship and; 8) Cultural awareness and expression (2018, p. 15). The key competences are all considered equally important; each of them contributes to a successful life in society. According the same council (2018, p. 14): *"These can be applied in many different contexts and in a variety of combinations. They overlap and interlock; aspects essential to one domain will support competence in another. Skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, teamwork, communication and negotiation skills, analytical skills, creativity, and intercultural skills are embedded throughout the key competences."* These skills are the most reported for the 21st century (Kang, 2019; The Economist, 2015; UNESCO, 2016; World Economic Forum, 2015).

The competence-oriented education could be promoted in formal context, as well as in informal, through activities promoted by the teacher but also by their peers in a network of collaboration (Zhang et al., 2008). The learning should take place, independently, of the space, time and relations in a fluid approach (Kang, 2019; UNESCO, 2015). In the education system these competencies are promoted by adopting more effective learning methodologies, suitable environment and experiential learning to stimulate these competencies (Anabela C. Alves et al., 2018; Bonwell & Eison, 1991; Felder & Brent, 2006; Fernandes, 2014; Freeman et al., 2014; Gibbs & Habeshaw, 1992; Shapiro, 2014). At the same time, these learning methodologies should be supported by digital technologies (High Level Group on the Modernisation of Higher Education, 2013; Uebe-Mansur et al., 2019; Vicente et al., 2014). Due to the declared COVID-19 pandemic crisis in March of 2020, teachers, students and parents are rapidly learning how to use such digital technologies. This means that such experiential is gained if students are involved in real-world contexts what could be achieved with partnerships with companies and/or active learning contexts (Council of the European Union, 2018; Kang, 2019; Nair et al., 2009; Pellegrino & Hilton, 2012; UNESCO, 2010).

This need to provide active learning environment and conditions for the students to connect the disciplinary contents of different courses was the motivation for the paper authors to offer an interdisciplinary project among two courses of Industrial Engineering and Management third year, first semester (IEM31). This interdisciplinary project was requested as an assignment to do in the context of Production System Organization I and Process Control and Automation. In this paper, this interdisciplinary project is presented with two main purposes: 1) describe the teamwork outcomes, showing the contents integration of the two courses and 2) discusses the questionnaire results, highlighting the key competences developed through examples of students outcomes and knowledge, skills and attitudes assumed by them during the project developed and hands-on activity.

This paper is divided in five sections. After this first introduction, the research methodology is presented. The study context is described in section three, while section four presents the results analysis and discussion. Finally, section five depicts some concluding remarks.

2 Research methodology

The research strategy follows a case study (IEM third year) through a qualitative approach by using questionnaires as the technique for data collection and result analysis. To fulfil the defined objectives for the paper, the teams outcomes related with contents integration of the two courses will be presented. Additionally, to discuss the key competences developed, it was used an on-line questionnaire results and teachers observations and experience. This questionnaire has been used to evaluate the hands-on activity developed in the context of one of the teams' task assignment of PSOI course since 2016_17

The survey included 38 questions: 34 closed questions and four open-ended questions. The closed questions were scored in a Likert scale [1: Totally disagree to 5: Totally agree]. The questions of the questionnaire were in a simple language for the students understanding (e.g. "Question 1: After reading the task/work statement, I was curious and I looking forward immediate material for it execution." or "Question 2: "I did extra work for this task"). They were not settled with the purpose of analyse the competences but there is a strong relation with the competences. So, in a previous study, the authors classified and grouped the 34 closed questions in 15 categories related with competencies as characterized by Rychen and Salganik (2000). These results were presented in Alves and Soares (2020). For the study presented in this paper, it was used the skills embed in the eight key competences proposed by the Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (Council of the European Union, 2018), as referred in section 1. For example, question 1 above was related to

the attitude of the students when they read the task statement, if they get curious about that and look for material for it execution. This attitude reveals pro-activity, problem-solving skills that are embed in literacy and entrepreneurship competences.

3 Study context

This section gives an overview of Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) third year (IEM31). The IEM of University of Minho is a Master Integrated programme of five years, 10 semesters. Each semester has 5-6 courses of five European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) each in a total of 30 by semester. In the final of the programme students obtain 300 ECTS. This is so since 2006, when Bologna process was introduced in Portugal (Veiga & Amaral, 2009). With this, some Integrated Projects were included in engineering programmes. In IEM were included three Integrated projects in the first year, first semester and fourth year, both semesters. In a general way, students felt motivated by these and would like to have more projects (A.C. Alves et al., 2018). Others courses are organized in a compartmentalized way (Flumerfelt et al., 2014), with some exceptional interdisciplinary projects, as the one that was presented in Soares and Alves (2019) and it will be detailed in this paper.

3.1 Industrial Engineering and Management – third year, first semester

The third year, first semester of IEM includes the courses presented in Figure 1, being Production System Organization I (PSOI) and Process and Control Automation (PCA) two of them. These are briefly presented below.

S1	Energy, Environment and Industrial Systems	CE	5
S1	Process Control and Automation	CE	5
S1	Production Systems Organization I	CEsp	5
S1	Quality Engineering and Management	CE	5
S1	Stochastic Models of Operational Research	CCp; CEsp	5
S1	Opção Tecnológica III		5
	Apparel Production Technologies	CE	5
	Introduction to Polymers	CEP	5

Figure 1. Study plan of IEM third year, first semester (UMINHO, 2020)

The PSOI learning outcomes (LO) are settled as:

1. Identify different production paradigms;
2. Distinguish Lean Thinking principles and others methodologies that question the production system adequacy;
3. Distinguish wastes types and their impact on production systems;
4. Classify the production systems relating to different criteria;
5. Distinguish the main production systems type;
6. Project and organize production cells/lines:
 - a) Form parts families, using clustering algorithms or others criteria;
 - b) Instantiate production cells, calculate machines number;
 - c) Instantiate workstations, calculate takt time and operators number;
 - d) Balance lines/cells, applying heuristically methods;
 - e) Organize intracellular layout, applying layouts methods;
 - f) Select the operating mode more adequate and skills matrix;
 - g) Organize intercellular layout and integrate the whole system;
7. Simulate the operating modes working of a production cell.

To assess these LO, teacher defined with the students for 2019_20 academic year an assessment methodology that includes three components:

- 1) three quizzes, five minutes tests done in pairs (weight: 15%, 5% each);
- 2) two individual tests of one hour each (weight: 30%; 15% each); and
- 3) two assignments done in teams (weight: 55%; 10% 1st task + 45% 2nd task).

In previous years, the number of components were even higher, but the teacher recognizes that it was too much work, for her and for the students. The second task is the interdisciplinary project work that will be detailed in the next section and it is the base for this paper.

PCA learning outcomes are:

1. Identify the main problems related to industrial automation and control;
2. Distinguish between different input and output transducers, their characteristics and application;
3. Discuss the architectures and characteristics of the programmable logic controllers (PLC);
4. Design combinational controllers;
5. Design sequential controllers in different automation systems using Grafset.
6. Implement automation problems in ladder diagrams.

In 2019_20 academic year the PCA assessment methodology includes three components:

1. An individual test weighing 50%. The test has a minimum score of 7/20. The written test is carried out without consulting documents (if necessary a form with the main equations is provided). The test will explicitly indicate the contribution, in values, of each question.
2. A group work in simulation, the interdisciplinary project work that will be detailed in the next section and it is the base for this paper, that solves an automation and control problem with a weight of 40%. The work has a minimum grade of 8/20 and can be performed in a) a company selected by the group or b) a "virtual" company defined by the group. The project must include the specifications, selection of sensors and actuators to be used, Grafset and ladder diagram of the proposed automatic system. The work is mandatory.
3. Activities Flipped Classroom with a weight of 10%. The evaluation of this component takes into account student participation in the Flipped Classroom activities.

The approval grade of the course unit is 9.5 out of 20.

3.2 PSOI and PCA project work organization and assessment

The project work for PSOI and PCA is an assignment that was requested as an interdisciplinary project to the IEM31 students in two academic years: 2017_18 and 2019_20. Due to the sabbatical license of PCA lecturer in 2018_19, the interdisciplinary project work was not requested.

In the case of PSOI, since 2016_17, a similar task assignment has been requested to the IEM31 students as part of their assessment, being one of components assessments (with the highest weight), as explained in section 3.1. Also, in PCA a project work has been part of the assessment since 2014_15. The students had until 2017-18 to develop two different and independent works.

The goal of the project was to design and implement a virtual or real-world (in a company selected by the students) based automated assembly line of a product (designed by the students).

They should design the assembly line/cell by selecting the operating mode, estimating the demand for the product, defining the operations and calculating all the necessary elements, balancing, and the supply mode. Students should also preview an automated line, including the automation project specifications, selection of sensors and actuators, Grafset and ladder diagram of the proposed system. They should also include other techniques learned from other curricular if necessary.

Students were organized into 11 teams of seven to ten members each. From the 11 teams, nine went to companies to develop the project. Table 1 presents the number of students and teams in each year. In 2019/20 the number of students increased but the number of teams was kept; the teams were bigger. It is worth pointing out that some students were only enrolled in PCA and they were not considered in this analysis.

Table 1. Number of students and teams in each academic year

Academic year	PSOI		PCA	
	Nº of students	Nº of teams	Nº of students	Nº of teams
2017/18	72	11	82	11
2019/20	92	11	105	11

As mentioned before, the overall assessment of the work contributes with 40% of the final grade in each course. The criteria used by each curricular unit is presented in the Table 2.

The type of materials submitted for evaluation had no pre-defined format. Students were allowed to choose the type that they considered the best (novelty was valued): video, PowerPoint, simulations, poster, web page, blog, and the traditional report. Students should explicitly state the contribution of each team member in the development of the work.

In the end, a one-day public presentation of the projects was scheduled. The 30-minutes presentation included also the demonstration of the production cells to obtain the designed product, demonstrating and measuring some performance variables by performing the hands-on activity.

Table 2. Assessment criteria of each curricular unit

Criteria PSOI	Criteria PCA	eight
Preparation and creativity	Automation system design. Presentation of documentation	1
Contents exploration		1
Presentation and exposition	Public presentation	2
Demonstration and simulation	Grafcet and ladder diagram of automatic system	2
Results and discussion	Critical evaluation of final project	1
Materials delivery on time	Materials delivery on time	5

4 Contents integration and key competences developed

This section presents the team outcomes, highlighting contents integration, as well as the analysis of the results obtained through the on-line questionnaire filled by the students.

4.1 Interdisciplinary contents integration: teamwork outcomes

In this edition, teachers used padlet (<https://padlet.com/>), Figure 2, as a means to share information and as a repository of the project works. Project rules and videos from previous works were publicize in the first column. Each group had a dedicated column where they put in the information related to the project development and considered relevant for evaluation: tasks, meeting outcomes, company visits, work developed, simulations and videos, documents, links to webpages. Padlet is an appropriate means of sharing information, while allowing transparency, and a healthy competition, between teams.

Figure 2. Padlet with the whole vision of teams work and simulations (2019_2020)

All teams simulated the production of a good in a production cell, organizing people in the cell according to a previously selected operating mode. In the cell/line is included automated production subsystem components.

All the teams fulfilled the requisites of integrating PSO I and PCA contents in the designed cell/line production. One example of this integration is presented in Figure 3. The group worked in a real company dedicated to the production of cheese. Students designed the best layout (on the left) in order to optimize production parameters as well as they designed an automated filling machine (on the right).

Figure 3. One team project outcome: Cheese production, layout and filling machine draft.

4.2 Key competences developed: on-line questionnaire results

The discussion in this section is based on the key competences and skills defined by the Council of the European Union (2018) and presented in the section 1. This discussion is partially based on the questionnaire questions developed for the hands-on activity, by analyzing the students answers of the academic year 2017/18 and 2019/20. The response rate was of 21% in 2017/18 and in the 2019/20 it was almost 50%.

Attending to the eight skills embed in the eight key competences referred in the Council of the European Union (2018), the 34 questions of the survey were classified and grouped around these eight skills. Because some of the questions were not clear which skill belongs, the paper authors added the "Learning to learn" to this list. After obtaining the average for each question, it was obtained the average for each skill group for each academic year. The results of this study is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Results of on-line questionnaire results

Some of the questions were not reflected in these skills because they were designed by the negative side, i.e., related with passive attitude of the students. For example, these three were: "The main reason for completing the task was to perform the course requirements", "I did the task to avoid the blame of not doing" or "The classes where I just have to be "present" are the best." The average of these questions received a score of 2,3 that was a low score.

The open questions were related what the students enjoy more in the hands-on activity. The words cloud in Figure 5 shows the most referred words. It is possible to highlight the words *company* and *practice*. Others are much related with the skills referred: teamwork, problem-solving, applied theory, learning to learn, among others.

a)

b)

Figure 5. What the students enjoy more in the hands-on activity: a) 2017/18; b) 2019/20

What pleased least in the first edition were the unbalancing workload among all team members, short duration for this assignment, the missing assessment criteria, difficulties to the product presentation in a classroom, the lack of sync among company and teacher objectives, the difficulty in interpreting the task statement (Figure 6).

a)

b)

Figure 6. What the students enjoy less in the hands-on activity: a) 2017/18; b) 2019/20

The students were very critical and made some recommendations to improve the task assignment. Some were attended. Other were not attended due to the objectives of the activity defined by the teachers, namely, to have a template for the presentation, to have more specifications for the simulation, to have a previously defined operating mode, have a previous contact with companies made by teachers. Teachers did not attend to suggestions because they did not accomplish the objective of the teachers that want to stimulate students creativity and initiative. Students also recommend more time for the simulation and discussion. Students also pointed out the lack of attention in all presentations (remember that are 11 presentations of 30 minutes each), the team dimension (seven to 10 members), the lack of interest of some team members. Some students (are third graders) continues in an immature state and preferred to be commanded, instead of taking decisions. What is understandable because many people, according to the Theory X of Douglas McGregor (Chapman, 2002), felt more comfortable when someone tells them what to do. More about the survey results could be consulted in Alves and Soares (2020).

Nevertheless, it is important to discuss knowledge, skills and attitudes embed in the competencies. Due to the limited space of the paper, just four out of the eight most striking were chosen and discussed through some examples retrieved from the elements delivered by the students, their presentation and hands-on activity, their attitude in the contact with the companies (it was optional, but nine teams preferred to do the work in companies). Table 3 presents these examples.

Table 3. Examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes related to competencies acquired by the students

Competencies	Knowledge	Skills	Attitudes
Mathematical, science, technology and engineering	Calculate takt time, number of operators, KPI, develop grafkets, transform company data in graphs	Apply the operating mode in the production system designed and design the automated system	Build the products prototypes resemble real companies products
Digital	Be aware of new tools to communicate	Digital tools use (e.g. Padlet, videos)	Initiative to use different tools, to share information
Personal, social and learning to learn	Plan a project and activities, plan, distribute individual and team tasks, establish a contact with a company, public presentation	Go & See in the Gemba (as requested by lean theory), negotiate and solve conflicts, Initiative to present a topic and answer to questions; role-play	Initiative to develop prototypes; communicate with companies, how to act in public
Entrepreneurship	Manage a project with a company and collaborate in a big team; creativity by developing the prototypes; attend meetings with CEOs or technical directors	Build the products prototypes, mobilize resources; Initiative to contact local industries	Stimulus and motivation to make the project, leading with company unavailability

5 Conclusion

This paper presents an interdisciplinary project developed between two courses of IEM third year, first semester. These courses are lectured by teachers belonging to different departments and expertise areas, that complements each other. Nevertheless, students are many times unaware of this complementarity, as the courses have been lectured as silo-discipline. With this project, teachers intended to close this gap, contributing for a more holistic view of the courses, at least of these two. By the perspective of the students, this seems being achieved. Also the evidences of students work, reveals they were beyond the knowledge, acquiring

competencies. With this type of project, competences as entrepreneurship, personal and social skills are promoted in parallel to engineering and technical expertise. For future work, the authors have in mind to improve the questionnaire to include more competence-related questions.

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